

Adapting CLIL for Uzbek Secondary Schools: Pedagogical Opportunities and Institutional Challenges

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Abstract: This article aims to research the implementation of Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) in Uzbek secondary schools, addressing the ways of enhancement of applying dual-focused approach of both language proficiency and subject matter understanding. It examines the current state of English language education in Uzbekistan, points out core barriers to apply CLIL more effectively in sustainable education system.

Keywords: CLIL, secondary schools, curriculum reform, Uzbekistan, student-centered pedagogy, language policy, teacher training, public vs. private schools.

Introduction. Since Uzbekistan has carried on reforming its educational system to adapt international standards, CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning), as innovative pedagogical methods are becoming increasingly relevant. CLIL integrates academic content through a foreign language, promoting students to enhance both subject knowledge and language proficiency simultaneously (Coyle, Hood, & Marsh, 2010).

Although policy initiatives have aimed to modernize language education, English lessons in most Uzbek schools remain grammar-focused and teacher-centered learning. This traditional method of teaching does not cultivate communicative skills and critical thinking. The integration of CLIL would reinforce student-centered approaches, advance learner engagement, foster cognitive development, and support the enhancement of real-life language use through science, history, and math.

Methods.

This current research applies both qualitative and quantitative approaches to get aware of the present state of CLIL practices in Uzbekistan. Study methods relay on a survey of 100 English and subject teachers from 20 secondary schools in Tashkent, Bukhara, and Ferghana regions. Additionally, there are classroom observations in both rural and urban areas to weigh up CLIL and traditional methods, interviews with school administrators and curriculum developers. Finally, international CLIL case studies analysis of Spain, Finland, Kazakhstan, and Estonia.

Literature Review

Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) has been efficiently implemented in bilingual and multilingual education in European countries for past three decades. As it was emphasized at the beginning, initially, CLIL was designed to advance subject learning and foreign language simultaneously to enhance cognitive development, cultural awareness, and academic achievement (Coyle, Hood, & Marsh, 2010; Mehisto, Marsh, & Frigols, 2008).

Several researches reviews affirm CLIL's effectiveness. The *Eurydice Report* (2006) notes the increasing implementation of CLIL in European schools, where high level of language proficiency empowers subjects matter comprehension. Similarly, the OECD (2018) points out the use of CLIL method increase 21st-century skills: critical thinking, collaboration, and global citizenship.

Case studies from Kazakhstan and Estonia (e.g., Mehisto, 2012) recommend that CLIL can be significantly successful when supported by teacher training and flexible national policies. According

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to the results of those countries, gradual implementation, political supports are essential to sustainable integration.

Bilingual education still remains mostly experimental in Uzbekistan. The Ministry of Public Education of Uzbekistan (2022) highlights the strategic value of English Proficiency, there is not a single plan for embedding it into subject instruction, specifically in public-sectors.

All in all, localized research in Central Asia, particularly in Uzbekistan, is still scarce, despite the fact that international literature offers support for the educational efficacy of CLIL. This study seeks that gap by assessing both institutional capacity and teacher readiness in Uzbek secondary schools by providing well-founded insights for CLIL adaption in post-Soviet educational systems.

Results

According to the result of survey, only 12% of schools, in private and international schools in Uzbekistan, CLIL has been integrating. 76% of educators expressed passion in CLIL. However, they mentioned several barriers, such as lack of training, instructional materials, and bilingual competence. Despite CLIL promoting a friendly atmosphere, high-level student engagement, and task-based learning, there is a catch in minor administrative support in most public schools.

Why does it occur in governmental schools compared to non-governmental schools?

Governmental institutions are characterized by rigid curricula standards and teacher-centered approaches. Implementation of CLIL is limited, due to lack of English proficiency among subject teachers, bilingual textbooks. By contrast, non-governmental institutions are independent with more flexible curricula, specifically cross-curricular planning between language and subject teachers and offer better resources. CLIL methods are efficiently integrated in science, ICT, and humanities subjects, as educators have received specialized training, regular professional workshops on CLIL methods, and classrooms are equipped with up-graded digital tools and resources.

Barriers in Governmental Schools and How to Overcome Them:

1. Shortage of Qualified Educators:

Solution: Launch CLIL teacher training programs in cooperation with universities and international agencies.

2. Strictly Structured Curriculum:

Solution: Test CLIL-modules in elective subjects or after-school activities to demonstrate if they work before integrating them into the main curriculum.

3. Lack of Resources:

Solution: Enhance accessibility of CLIL teaching materials and encourage the utilization of low-tech solutions (e.g., bilingual posters, visuals aids).

4. Opposition to Pedagogical Reform:

Solution: Conduct CLIL research within Uzbekistan and offer indirect incentives for innovative teaching practices.

Discussion

International practice has claimed that CLIL advances language proficiency, without compromising difficulty mastery. In Finland and the Basque Country (Spain), students with excellent bilingual skills and academic performances have been noticed while utilizing CLIL programs. These programs achieved appealing success due to structured teacher schooling, logical curricular, and bilingual education support.

Several strategic steps should begin with while integrating CLIL in Uzbekistan:

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- Gradual Integration: Use CLIL step-by-step, starting with bilingual images, terminology before diving into fully English-taught content.
- Teacher Retraining: Create CLIL-focused certification programs in pedagogical institutions, specifically, in association with British Council and European universities.
- Curriculum Reform: Modernize national curricula to add language and material more easily. Offer subject teachers' flexible courses without requiring complete English proficiency.
- Resource Development: Produce digital learning environments, bilingual textbooks, and appropriate materials for regional contexts.
- Collaborative Teaching: Promote cooperation between English and subject teachers to collaborate while designing lesson plans.

Conclusion and Suggestions

CLIL provides a creative and effective technique to advance Uzbek students' academic and language performance. Teacher empowerment, institutional change, and long-term planning are crucial for effective integration. The evidence suggests that the followings must be done:

1. Policy Development: Provide a national CLIL application roadmap promoted by the Ministry of Public Education.
2. Pilot Schools: Start demonstration schools in each region to show as models for CLIL best practices.
3. Capacity Buildings: Advance teachers' CLIL competencies through promoting scholarships, online courses, and workshops.
4. Public-Private Partnerships: Corporation between private and NGO institutions in resource creation and teacher training.
5. Monitoring and Assessment: Evolve reliable measures to evaluate the impact of CLIL on student performance and teacher effectiveness.

Uzbekistan may establish a future-ready education system through the comprehension of global models and localized experimentation, in which English functions not only as a subject but also as a torch for lifelong learning and international cooperation.

References:

1. Coyle, D., Hood, P., & Marsh, D. (2010). *CLIL: Content and language integrated learning* (Vol. 1). Cambridge: Cambridge university press.
2. Eurydice. (2006) *Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) at schools in Europe*. Brussels: European Commission.
3. Mehisto, P., Marsh, D., & Frigols, M. J. (2008). *Uncovering CLIL: Content and integrated language learning in bilingual and multilingual education*. (No Title).
4. Ministry of Public Education of Uzbekistan (2022). *National Strategy for English Language Learning Development*
5. OECD. (2018). *The future of Education and Skills: Education 2030*. OECD publishing.
6. Samievna, T. S., Mirkomilovna, R. M., & Obidovich, K. V. (2021). *The professional pedagogical activity in modern education*. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(9), 275-277.
7. Akbarov, K., Alimov, N., Otazhonov, S. M., & Khomidov, V. O. (2010). *The external impact on photoelectric properties of nano-crystal p-CdTe films*.
8. UNESCO. (2021). *Reimagining our future together: A new social contract for education*. UNESCO Publishing.

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9. British Council. Retrieved from <https://www.teachingenglish.org.uk/professional-development/teachers/educational-policies-practices/articles/content-and-language>

